

The Riemann Transform

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ABSTRACT

In his 1859 paper, Bernhard Riemann used the integral equation $\int_0^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx$ to develop an explicit formula for estimating the number of primes less than a given quantity. It is the purpose of this present work to explore some of the properties of this equation.

Introduction

Consider the integral equation given below

$$(1) \quad F\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx.$$

Formula (1) is the integral of $f(x)$ times x^{-s-1} for $x = 0$ to ∞ and the resulting integral is denoted by $F\{s\}$ (or the **transform** of f). It must be assumed that $f(x)$ is such that $|F\{s\}| < \infty$ and s is a complex constant or single-valued. Since s is constant, Δs and ΔF are both zero. So that

$$\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s} = \frac{0}{0} = \text{indeterminate}, \quad \text{and} \quad \int_s^s F\{s\} ds = 0.$$

Since $\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s}$ and $\frac{dF}{ds}$ do not exist, which proves $F\{s\}$ is *not* a function but is a constant.

The constant $F\{s\}$ is also single-valued, that is

$$F\{s\} = \begin{cases} F\{s\} & s = s \\ 0 & \text{not } s \end{cases}$$

Example 1: Apply formula (1) to obtain the transform of $f(x) = e^{-x}$.

Solution. Substitute e^{-x} to (1)

$$F\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{-s-1} dx = \Gamma\{-s\}, \quad \Re(s) < 0, \quad s = s \quad \text{since} \quad \Gamma(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-x} x^{s-1} dx, \quad \Re(s) > 0, \quad s = s$$

where $\Gamma\{s\}$ is the Gamma constant and $\Re(s)$ is the real part of s .

Unit Step Function (Heaviside Function)

The **unit step function** or **Heaviside function** $\mu(x-a)$ is 0 for $x < a$, has a jump size 1 at $x = a$ (where it is usually considered as undefined), and is 1 for $x > a$, in a formula:

$$\mu(x-a) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x < a \\ 1 & \text{if } x > a \end{cases} \quad a \geq 0.$$

The transform of $\mu(x-a)$ is

$$F\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} x^{-s-1} \mu(x-a) dx = \int_a^{\infty} x^{-s-1} dx = \left. \frac{-x^{-s}}{s} \right|_a^{\infty}$$

here the integration begins at $x = a (>0)$ because $\mu(x-a)$ is 0 for $x < a$. Hence

$$F\{s\} = \frac{a^{-s}}{s} \quad a > 0 \text{ and } \Re(s) > 0, \quad s = s.$$

Example 2: The Riemann zeta constant is given by

$$\zeta\{s\} = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad \Re(s) > 1, \quad s = s$$

obtain the transform of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mu(x-n)$, $n = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} F\{s\} &= \int_0^{\infty} \{\mu(x-1) + \mu(x-2) + \mu(x-3) + \dots\} x^{-s-1} dx = \left. \frac{-x^{-s}}{s} \right|_1^{\infty} + \left. \frac{-x^{-s}}{s} \right|_2^{\infty} + \left. \frac{-x^{-s}}{s} \right|_3^{\infty} + \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{s} (1 + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + \dots) = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \frac{\zeta\{s\}}{s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1, \quad s = s. \end{aligned}$$

Example 3: Obtain the transform of $\pi(x) = \sum_p \mu(x-p)$, where p is a prime number, $p = 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} F\{s\} &= \int_0^{\infty} \left\{ \sum_p \mu(x-p) x^{-s-1} dx \right\} = \int_0^{\infty} \{\mu(x-2) + \mu(x-3) + \mu(x-5) + \mu(x-7) + \dots\} x^{-s-1} dx \\ \Pi\{s\} &= \frac{1}{s} (2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 5^{-s} + 7^{-s} + \dots) = \frac{1}{s} \sum_p p^{-s} \quad \Re(s) > 1, \quad s = s. \end{aligned}$$

Dirac's Delta Function

Consider the function

$$f_{\tau}(x-a) = \begin{cases} 1/\tau & \text{if } a \leq x \leq a+\tau \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Its integral is

$$I = \int_0^{\infty} f_{\tau}(x-a) dx = \int_a^{a+\tau} \frac{1}{\tau} dx = 1.$$

We let now let τ becomes smaller and smaller and take the limit as $\tau \rightarrow 0$ ($\tau > 0$). This limit is denoted by $\delta(x-a)$, that is,

$$\delta(x-a) = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} f_{\tau}(x-a)$$

and obtain

$$\delta(x-a) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } x = a \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^{\infty} \delta(x-a) dx = 1.$$

$\delta(x-a)$ is called the **Dirac delta function** or the **unit impulse function**. For a *continuous* function $f(x)$ one uses the **sifting** property of $\delta(x-a)$,

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) \delta(x-a) dx = f\{a\}.$$

To obtain the transform of $\delta(x-a)$, we write

$$f_{\tau}(x-a) = \frac{1}{\tau} \{ \mu(x-a) - \mu(x-(a+\tau)) \}$$

and take the transform

$$F\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} f_{\tau}(x-a) x^{-s-1} dx = \frac{1}{\tau} \int_a^{a+\tau} x^{-s-1} dx \quad a > 0.$$

As τ approaches zero, the function x^{-s-1} (from a to $a+\tau$) is essentially constant, that is

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} x^{-(s+1)} = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} (a+\tau)^{-(s+1)} = a^{-(s+1)}, \text{ so that}$$

$$F\{s\} = \frac{a^{-(s+1)}}{\tau} \int_a^{a+\tau} dx = \frac{a^{-(s+1)}}{\tau} (a+\tau-a) = a^{-(s+1)} \quad a > 0.$$

Example 4: Obtain the transform of $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x \delta(x-n)$ and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \delta(x-n)$.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x \delta(x-n) \right\} x^{-s-1} dx = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \zeta\{s\}, \quad \Re(s) > 1, \quad s=s.$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \delta(x-n) \right\} x^{-s-1} dx = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-(s+1)} = \zeta\{s+1\}, \quad \Re(s) > 0, \quad s=s.$$

The Riemann Transform

If $f(x)$ is a function defined for all $x \geq 1$, its **Riemann transform** is the integral of $f(x)$ times x^{-s-1} for $x = 1$ to ∞ . Let's denote it by $F\{s\}$ or $R\{f\}$,

$$(2) \quad F\{s\} = R\{f\} = \int_1^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx.$$

The given function $f(x)$ in (2) is called the **inverse transform** of $F\{s\}$ and is denoted by $R^{-1}\{F\}$; that is,

$$f(x) = R^{-1}\{F\}.$$

Example 5: Let $f(x) = 1$, find $F\{s\}$.

Solution. From (2) we obtain by integration

$$R\{f\} = R\{1\} = \int_1^{\infty} x^{-s-1} dx = -\frac{1}{s} x^{-s} \Big|_1^{\infty} = \frac{1}{s} \quad \Re(s) > 0, \quad s=s$$

Example 6: Let $f(x) = x^a$, where a is constant. Find $F\{s\}$.

Solution. From (2),

$$R\{x^a\} = \int_1^{\infty} x^a x^{-s-1} dx = -\frac{1}{s-a} x^{-(s-a)} \Big|_1^{\infty} = \frac{1}{s-a} \quad \Re(s-a) > 0.$$

THEOREM 1: Linearity of the Riemann Transform

The Riemann transform is a linear operation; that is, for any functions $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ whose transforms exist and any constants a and b the transform of $af(x) + bg(x)$ exists, and

$$R\{af(x) + bg(x)\} = aF(s) + bG(s).$$

Example 7: Find the transforms of $\cosh(a \ln x)$ and $\sinh(a \ln x)$.

Solution. Since $\cosh(a \ln x) = \frac{1}{2}(x^a + x^{-a})$ and $\sinh(a \ln x) = \frac{1}{2}(x^a - x^{-a})$, we obtain from Example 6 and Theorem 1,

$$R\{\cosh(a \ln x)\} = \frac{1}{2}(R(x^a) + R(x^{-a})) = \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{s-a} + \frac{1}{s+a}\right) = \frac{s}{s^2 - a^2}$$

$$R\{\sinh(a \ln x)\} = \frac{1}{2}(R(x^a) - R(x^{-a})) = \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{1}{s-a} - \frac{1}{s+a}\right) = \frac{a}{s^2 - a^2}.$$

Example 8: Let $f(x) = x^{\alpha i}$, where i is the imaginary operator ($i = \sqrt{-1}$). Find $F\{s\}$.

Solution. From Example 6

$$R\{x^{\alpha i}\} = \frac{1}{s - \alpha i} = \frac{1}{s - \alpha i} \frac{s + \alpha i}{s + \alpha i} = \frac{s}{s^2 + \alpha^2} + i \frac{\alpha}{s^2 + \alpha^2}.$$

Example 9: Cosine and Sine

Derive the formulas

$$R\{\cos(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{s}{s^2 + \alpha^2} \quad \text{and} \quad R\{\sin(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{\alpha}{s^2 + \alpha^2}.$$

Solution. From Example 8 and Theorem 1

$$x^{\alpha i} = \cos(\alpha \ln x) + i \sin(\alpha \ln x)$$

$$R\{x^{\alpha i}\} = R\{\cos(\alpha \ln x)\} + i R\{\sin(\alpha \ln x)\}, \text{ thus}$$

$$R\{\cos(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{s}{s^2 + \alpha^2} \quad \text{and} \quad R\{\sin(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{\alpha}{s^2 + \alpha^2}.$$

THEOREM 2: s-Shifting Theorem

If $f(x)$ has the transform $F(s)$ (where $s > k$ for some k), then $x^a f(x)$ has the transform $F\{s - a\}$ (where $s - a > k$). In formulas,

$$R\{x^a f(x)\} = F\{s - a\}$$

or, if we take the inverse on both sides $x^a f(x) = R^{-1}\{F\{s - a\}\}$.

PROOF: We obtain $F\{s - a\}$ by replacing s with $s - a$ in the integral in (1), so that

$$F\{s - a\} = \int_1^{\infty} x^{-(s-a)-1} f(x) dx = \int_1^{\infty} x^{-s-1} [x^a f(x)] dx = R\{x^a f(x)\}.$$

Example 10: From Example 9 and the s-Shifting theorem one can obtain the Riemann transform for

$$R\{x^a \cos(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{s-a}{(s-a)^2 + \alpha^2} \quad \text{and} \quad R\{x^a \sin(\alpha \ln x)\} = \frac{\alpha}{(s-a)^2 + \alpha^2}.$$

Existence and Uniqueness of Riemann Transforms

A function $f(x)$ has a Riemann transform if it does not grow too fast, say, if for all $x \geq 1$ and some constants M and k it satisfies

$$(3) \quad |f(x)| \leq Mx^k.$$

THEOREM 3: Existence Theorem for Riemann Transforms

If $f(x)$ is defined and piecewise continuous on every finite interval on $x \geq 1$ and satisfies (3) for all $x \geq 1$ and some constants M and k , then the Riemann transform $R\{f\}$ exists for all $s > k$.

PROOF Since $f(x)$ is piecewise continuous, $x^{-s-1}f(x)$ is integrable over any finite interval on the x -axis,

$$|R\{f\}| = \left| \int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-1} dx \right| \leq \int_1^{\infty} |f(x)|x^{-s-1} dx \leq \int_1^{\infty} Mx^k x^{-s-1} dx = \frac{M}{s-k}.$$

Uniqueness. If the Riemann transform of a given function exists, it is uniquely determined and if two continuous functions have the same transform, they are completely identical.

Transforms of Derivatives

THEOREM 4: Riemann Transform of Derivatives

The transforms of the first and second derivatives of $f(x)$ satisfy

$$(4) \quad R\{f'\} = (s+1)F\{s+1\} - f(1)$$

$$(5) \quad R\{f''\} = (s+2)(s+1)F\{s+2\} - (s+1)f(1) - f'(1)$$

Formula (4) holds if $f(x)$ is continuous for all $x \geq 1$ and satisfies (3) and $f'(x)$ is piecewise continuous on every finite interval for $x \geq 1$. Formula (5) holds if f and f' are continuous for all $x \geq 1$ and satisfy (3) and f'' is piecewise continuous on every finite interval for $x \geq 1$.

PROOF: Using integration by parts on formula (4)

$$R\{f'\} = \int_1^{\infty} f'(x)x^{-s-1}dx = [f(x)x^{-s-1}]_1^{\infty} + (s+1)\int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-2}dx = -f(1) + (s+1)F\{s+1\}.$$

The proof of (5) now follows by applying integration by parts twice on it, that is

$$\begin{aligned} R\{f''\} &= \int_1^{\infty} f''(x)x^{-s-1}dx = [f'(x)x^{-s-1}]_1^{\infty} + (s+1)\int_1^{\infty} f'(x)x^{-s-2}dx \\ &= -f'(1) + (s+1)\left[f(x)x^{-s-2}\Big|_1^{\infty} + (s+2)\int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-3}dx \right] \\ &= -f'(1) - (s+1)f(1) + (s+2)(s+1)F\{s+2\}. \end{aligned}$$

Repeatedly using integration by parts as in the proof of (5) and using induction, we obtain the following Theorem.

THEOREM 5: Riemann Transform of the Derivative $f^{(n)}$ of Any Order

Let $f, f', \dots, f^{(n-1)}$ be continuous for all $x \geq 1$ and satisfy (2). Furthermore, let $f^{(n)}$ be piecewise continuous on every finite interval for $x \geq 1$. Then the transform of $f^{(n)}$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} R\{f^{(n)}\} &= (s+n)(s+n-1)\cdots(s+1)F\{s+n\} - (s+n-1)(s+n-2)\cdots f(1) - \\ &\quad (s+n-2)(s+n-3)\cdots f'(1) - \cdots - f^{(n-1)}(1). \end{aligned}$$

Example 11: Let $f(x) = x^2$. Then $f(1) = 1$, $f'(x) = 2x$, $f'(1) = 2$, $f''(x) = 2$. Obtain $R\{f\}$, $R\{f'\}$, and $R\{f''\}$.

Solution. $R\{f\} = F\{s\} = \frac{1}{s-2}$, $F\{s+1\} = \frac{1}{s-1}$, $F\{s+2\} = \frac{1}{s}$. Hence, by formulas (4) and (5),

$$R(f') = (s+1)\frac{1}{s-1} - 1 = \frac{2}{s-1} \quad \text{and} \quad R(f'') = (s+2)(s+1)\frac{1}{s} - (s+1) - 2 = \frac{2}{s}.$$

The Riemann Transform and the Laplace Transform

The Laplace transform is the integral of $f(y)$ times e^{-sy} from $y = 0$ to ∞ where $f(y)$ is defined for all $y \geq 0$. It is denoted by $L\{f\}$,

$$(6) \quad L\{f\} = \int_0^{\infty} f(y)e^{-sy} dy.$$

The Riemann transform is given below

$$(7) \quad R\{f\} = \int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-1} dx.$$

Replace $x = e^y$ (or $y = \ln x$) in formula (7) and since $x = 1$ to ∞ , $y = 0$ ($\ln 1$) to ∞ ($\ln \infty$).

$$\int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-1} dx = \int_0^{\infty} f(e^y)e^{-sy-y} d(e^y) = \int_0^{\infty} f(y)e^{-sy} dy,$$

which is formula (6).

The Bilateral Laplace Transform

Formula (6) is usually called the **Unilateral** Laplace transform since the integral is evaluated from 0 to ∞ . The integral below is known as the Bilateral Laplace transform because the integral is taken from $-\infty$ to ∞ ,

$$(8) \quad B\{f\} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y)e^{-sy} dy.$$

Now, consider the integral equation

$$(9) \quad \int_0^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx,$$

Replace $x = e^y$ (or $y = \ln x$) in formula (9) and since $x = 0$ to ∞ , $y = -\infty$ to ∞ , thus

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(e^y) e^{-ys-y} d(e^y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y) e^{-sy} dy,$$

which is (8).

Riemann Transform: General Formulas

Formula	Name
$F\{s\} = R\{f(x)\} = \int_1^{\infty} f(x) x^{-s-1} dx$ $f(x) = R^{-1}\{F\{s\}\}$	<p>Definition of Transform</p> <p>Inverse Transform</p>
$R\{af(x) + bg(x)\} = aR\{f(x)\} + bR\{g(x)\}$	Linearity
$R\{x^a f(x)\} = F\{s-a\}$ $R^{-1}\{F\{s-a\}\} = x^a f(x)$	s-Shifting Theorem
$R\{f'\} = (s+1)F\{s+1\} - f(1)$ $R\{f''\} = (s+2)(s+1)F\{s+2\} - (s+1)f(1) - f'(1)$	Differentiation of Function

Table: Some Riemann Transforms

	$f(x) = R^{-1}\{F\{s\}\}$	$F\{s\} = \int_1^{\infty} f(x)x^{-s-1}dx$
1	1	$\frac{1}{s}$
2	x	$\frac{1}{s-1}$
3	x^a	$\frac{1}{s-a}$
4	$x^{\alpha i}$	$\frac{1}{s-\alpha i}$
5	$\cos(\alpha \ln x)$	$\frac{s}{s^2 + \alpha^2}$
6	$\sin(\alpha \ln x)$	$\frac{\alpha}{s^2 + \alpha^2}$
7	$\cosh(a \ln x)$	$\frac{s}{s^2 - a^2}$
8	$\sinh(a \ln x)$	$\frac{a}{s^2 - a^2}$
9	$x^b \cos(\alpha \ln x)$	$\frac{s-b}{(s-b)^2 + \alpha^2}$
10	$x^b \sin(\alpha \ln x)$	$\frac{\alpha}{(s-b)^2 + \alpha^2}$
11	$\frac{2}{\ln x} \{1 - \cos(\alpha \ln x)\}$	$\ln\left(\frac{s^2 + \alpha^2}{s^2}\right)$
12	$\frac{1}{\ln x} \sin(\alpha \ln x)$	$\arctan \frac{\alpha}{s}$
13	$\frac{2}{\ln x} \{1 - \cosh(a \ln x)\}$	$\ln\left(\frac{s^2 - a^2}{s^2}\right)$
14	$\frac{1}{\ln x} (x^b - x^a)$	$\ln\left(\frac{s-a}{s-b}\right)$

REFERENCE

Riemann, Bernhard (1859). *On the Number of Prime Numbers less than a Given Quantity*. pp. 5-7.